

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

MICAH MARIE G. BERNALES

SPECIES DIVERSITY, COMMUNITY STRUCTURE AND CARBON STOCK OF
MANGROVE FOREST 3-YEAR POST OCCURRENCE OF TYPHOON RAI
(ODETTE): THE CASE OF HONDA BAY, SNAKE ISLAND, PUERTO PRINCESA,
PALAWAN, PHILIPPINES

Special Problem Adviser:

CONSUELO DL. HABITO, PhD.
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

22 APRIL 2024

Permission is given for the following people to have access to this Special Problem, subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention(I)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
Publication(P)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
Confidential(C)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
Free(F)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input type="checkbox"/>	No

Student's signature:

Special Problem adviser:

University Permission Page

SPECIES DIVERSITY, COMMUNITY STRUCTURE AND CARBON STOCK OF MANGROVE FOREST 3-YEAR POST OCCURRENCE OF TYPHOON RAI (ODETTE): THE CASE OF HONDA BAY, SNAKE ISLAND, PUERTO PRINCESA, PALAWAN, PHILIPPINES

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this special problem in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IRR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. To upload a copy of the work in the special problem database of the college/school/institute/ department and in any other databases available on the public internet;*
- b. To publish the work in the college/school/institute /department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. To give open access to above-mentioned work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provisions of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.”*

Micah Marie G. Bernales and 22 April 2024

Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This special problem titled "**SPECIES DIVERSITY, COMMUNITY STRUCTURE AND CARBON STOCK OF MANGROVE FOREST 3-YEAR POST OCCURRENCE OF TYPHOON RAI (ODETTE): THE CASE OF HONDA BAY, SNAKE ISLAND, PUERTO PRINCESA, PALAWAN, PHILIPPINES**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

CONSUELO DL. HABITO, PHD.
Faculty-in-charge, ENRM 290 (Special Problem)

05 Sept 2024

(Date)

KARL ABELARD L. VILLEGAS, JR.
Program Chair

29 AUGUST 2024

(Date)

JOANE V. SERRANO

Dean

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

09 September 2024

Date

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

MICAH MARIE G. BERNALES
Name

Acknowledgement

First and foremost, I would like to give gratitude and praise to **God**, the Almighty, for His numerous blessings that enabled me to successfully complete my research.

I want to thank **Dr. Consuelo L. Habito**, my adviser, for allowing me the chance to do research and for her crucial advice during this process. She has taught me how to do research and how to communicate the findings as clearly as possible. Being able to work and learn under her direction was an immense privilege. I am truly grateful for what she has provided for me.

I would also like to thank **Prof. Karl Abelard Edberto L. Villegas, Jr.**, program chair and member of the panel, for his thoughtfulness in adhering to academic requirements.

I am extremely grateful to my parents, **Clarizza F. Galapon and Christyn B. Galapon**, who has inspired me to pursue my life's meaningful purpose, and I am exceedingly thankful of their love, prayers, care, and sacrifices in providing me with an education and equipped for the future environment.

I owe a lot of gratitude to my spouse, **Francis Clinton N. Bernales**, for his unwavering love, patience, prayers, and support during this study.

I want to express my gratitude to my coworkers. **For. Alvin S. Gestiada** and **For. John Rommel F. Manahan**, who supports and assists me in gathering data, I appreciate your sincere assistance during this study.

I also want to thank **Diana Riza A. Africa**, my batchmate, for the last three years of fun, memories, and support system. I also want to thank her for the extended hours we spent working together before deadlines.

I would like to express my gratitude to the **Faculty of Management and Development Studies** for helping me to successfully complete my course.

Upon the completion of this study, I am extending my thanks to everyone who contributed a key role in this journey.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTERS	PAGE
Title Page	Error! Bookmark not defined.
University Acceptance Page	i
Acceptance Page:.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
DECLARATION	iv
Acknowledgement	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	vii
LIST OF TABLES	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	x
LIST OF APPENDICES	xi
Abstract	xii
I. INTRODUCTION.....	1
II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	4
Overall importance of mangrove forests	4
Carbon stock in mangroves.....	5
Threats to mangrove forests.....	5
Regeneration potential of mangrove forests	6
Diversity of mangrove ecosystem.....	7
Structural characteristics of mangrove ecosystem	8
III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY.....	9
IV. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY.....	10
V. RATIONALE.....	11
VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS.....	12
VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA	13
VIII. METHODOLOGY	15
Field Data Collection	15
Species Diversity and Community Structure.....	17
Biomass Carbon Stock (Total Biomass of Standing Timber)	18
Statistical Analysis.....	19
IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.....	20
SPECIES COMPOSITION.....	20
Species Diversity, Community Structure and Carbon Stock of Mangrove Forest 3-Year Post Occurrence of Typhoon Rai (Odette): The Case of Honda Bay, Snake Island, Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Philippines	vii

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS	23
Diameter-at-breast-Height (DBH), Height, and Basal Area	23
Species abundance/density	24
Importance Value	25
SPECIES DIVERSITY	28
BIOMASS CARBON STOCK.....	30
Stocking classification	32
MANGROVE COVER BETWEEN 2021 and 2024.....	35
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS	40
Diversity.....	40
Biomass Carbon Stock.....	42
X. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION	44
XI. REFERENCES.....	47
XII. APPENDICES.....	Err

or! Bookmark not defined.

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE	PAGE
1	Coordinates of the 17 plots established in the island13
2	Species observed in the study site21
3	Mean Basal Area, DBH and Height of species present in the area.....23
4	Relative values and dominance of the species in the study site.....26
5	Mangrove species present in each sampling station27
6	Species Diversity of Mangroves in Snake Island in between 2021 and 202428
7	Total Biomass C stock (MgC ha ⁻¹) per species32
8	DENR (1998) and FAO (1996) stocking categorization based on mangrove density (individuals ha ⁻¹)33
9	Mangrove density (Trees ha ⁻¹) and classification of the sampling site..33
10	Comparative data on the structure of Snake Island 3-year post occurrence of Typhoon Rai (Odette)35
11	ANOVA of Shannon Diversity Index between 2021 and 2024.....41
12	ANOVA of the Shannon Diversity Index between42
13	ANOVA of Biomass Carbon Stock between 2021 and 2024.....42
.	
14	ANOVA of Biomass Carbon Stock between Plots43

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURES	PAGE
1	Biomass allometric equations and wood density used in the study19
2	Sampling plots in Snake Island20
3	Species found in the island22
4	Species abundance at the study site25
5	Species Diversity of the 17 Plots in Snake Island Between 2021 and 202430
6	Total Biomass C stock (MgC ha ⁻¹) of each of the sampling plots31
7	Some of the pruned and dead trees observed in the island36
8	Mangrove cover in 2021.....38
9	Mangrove cover in 2023.....38
10	Regeneration in parts of the mangrove area on the island39

LIST OF APPENDICES

APPENDICES	PAGE
1 Status of mangrove before typhoon Odette	51
2 Status of mangrove 3 years after typhoon Odette	52
3 Suffocation of sand resulting to higher mortality	53

Abstract

A healthy marine ecology is dependent on healthy mangrove forests. Mangroves provide vital ecosystem services such as coastal protection from storm damage and carbon sequestration potential that help mitigate the effects of climate change. This study aimed to assess the species diversity and structure as well as the biomass carbon stock content of mangrove vegetation in Honda Bay, Snake Island, Puerto Princesa, Palawan. Data from 2021 was compared to the data gathered in 2024, which accounts for the 3-year occurrence of Typhoon Rai (Odette). The non-destructive quadrat, the nested quadrat method was employed in the assessment to quantitatively describe the mangrove stand in a total of 17 plots. The data was analyzed to reveal if there is a difference in terms of diversity, structure, and carbon stock in the area from 2021 to 2024.

The result of the study found 7 mangrove species dominated by *Rhizophora stylosa* with 482 tree individuals because all of the mangrove tree planting activities that have taken place on the island in the past are more of this species and the presence of numerous mother trees facilitates its growth and survival. It has been observed that *Avicennia marina* and *Rhizophora stylosa* have the highest average basal area and DBH, giving them the highest importance value among other species with 219.85% and 38.42%, respectively. In the 2024 assessment, Plot 4 has 6 of the 7 mangrove species found on the island. This plot contains the most species and is the most diverse among the plots, with an index of 1.0810.

Results of this study revealed that the biomass carbon stock of mangroves in Snake Island ranged from 1.59 to 257.38 MgC ha⁻¹, or a mean of 75.56 MgC ha⁻¹, in 2021 and 2024. They differ only at the mean biomass carbon stock of 0.21 mg/ha.

In accordance with species composition, *Rhizophora stylosa* has the largest contribution to total biomass carbon stock in the island, with 14.26 MgC ha⁻¹ in the 2024 assessment, while *Rhizophora mucronata* bore the lowest with 0.49 MgC ha⁻¹. All of the sampling plots were under the category of adequately stocked or have highly dense forest cover, with a total density of 2,935 trees per ha computed using the data gathered in 2024.

From the 612 monitoring tree individuals before Typhoon Rai in December 2021 down to the 569 tree individuals or a total of 43 individuals monitored 3 years post-typhoon. Given the destruction caused by the typhoon throughout Palawan, the 3-year post-evaluation of Snake Island revealed only a 7.03% decrease. This is most likely due to the observation that new shoots and stems regenerated from the destroyed mangrove trees, resulting in an increase of 0.63 hectares in mangrove cover on the island. Given the stated mortality rate in the 2024 assessment, the mangrove cover rises from 18.43 hectares to 19.06 hectares through natural regeneration.

According to the statistical analysis performed on the data collected in 2021 and 2024, there is a significant difference between the plots because of the number of individuals in each plot ($p = 0.001$), but there is no significant difference between the data collected in 2021 and 2024 in terms of diversity.

The data from 2021 and 2024 did not reveal a significant difference between the years when comparing the biomass carbon stock ($p = 0.991$). Nonetheless, there was a notable difference in the number of people in each plot between them ($p < 0.001$).

These findings suggest that mangrove vegetation in Snake Island, Palawan, consists of an amount of carbon, implying that to help preserve and protect the area's coastal resources that rely on mangrove forests, there is a need to assess the existing mangrove area regularly. The assessment of mangroves is critical to ensuring the proper management efforts of the various concerned entities in order to sustain the area's biodiversity conservation information. This would generate data and serve as the foundation for future plans and programs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mangroves are salt-tolerant and seed-bearing woody plants that thrive in coastal areas, particularly along tidal flats as well as in river mouths with brackish water. They are morphologically and physiologically unique organisms since they withstand the harsh conditions of tidal actions, winds, temperature and anaerobic substrates (Kathiresan and Bingham, 2001). Mangroves provide vital ecosystem services which include, among others, protection of coastal areas from storm damage and riverbank erosion; serve as windbreaker; dissipate impacts of tidal movement; spawning/nursery ground for commercially important fishes and other aquatic species; high carbon sequestration potential that help mitigate effects of climate change; serve as habitat for a wide array of biodiversity; ecotourism; and source of income from fish, shrimp culture and wood gathering of coastal communities (Alongi 2012; Spalding et al., 2014; Spalding and Parrett, 2019).

Recent estimates of global mangrove cover show that they are declining at an alarming rate. Thomas, et.al. (2017) suggested a rate of degradation over the period 1990-2000 estimated at 1% per year which is twice than that of terrestrial rain forests' loss (Mayaux, 2005). In the case of mangroves in the Philippines, which represent about 1.9% of the world's mangrove cover, major threats include: aquaculture, agriculture, urbanization and cutting for fuel and construction materials (Garcia et al., 2013). The mangrove forest area of the Philippines was about 500,000 hectares in 1920 in which 247,362 hectares remained in 2003 (FAO, 2007). Based on the latest data, mangrove cover had improved from 247, 362 ha in 2003 to 310,531 ha in 2012 (FMB, 2013). The increase has been attributed to the numerous mangrove planting/rehabilitation projects conducted by both government and public institutions which has been undertaken as early as the 1930s (Primavera, 2008).

In the case of Snake Island in Honda Bay, Puerto Princesa, Palawan, the total mangrove area is 36 hectares (NAMRIA, 2020). It is one of the small islands in Honda Bay, located in the eastern part of mainland Puerto Princesa in Palawan (Dalby and Sorensen 2002). The island has a long sandbar that resembles a snake when viewed from a vantage point (Cesar 2000).

With its white sand and reef formation, the island has been a destination for island hopping and snorkeling until the issuance of DAO No. 2011-12 on November 3, 2011. The order declared the island a National Coastal and Marine Center for Research (NCMCR) of the DENR and, at the same time, prohibited activities unrelated to research. The Snake Island NCMCR shall serve as a research facility for ICM towards national goals and the sustainable management of coastal and marine resources in Palawan. Specifically, it shall serve as a field station for applied research on the coastal and marine environment, ecotourism (e.g., principles and best practices), and terrestrial biodiversity in Puerto Princesa, Palawan (DENR, 2011).

Typhoon Odette, however, made landfall on the island in December 2021 and left into the West Philippine Sea. One of the typhoons making landfall in the Philippine area of responsibility is Typhoon Odette (Rai), which has a circumferential overcast as wide as Typhoon Yolanda (Haiyan) in 2013. This seriously damaged Puerto Princesa, destroying not only houses and many park facilities, but also the cave system, entire old-growth forests, and marine life (Fabro, 2022).

This study evaluated the effect of Typhoon Rai's 3-year post-occurrence in Puerto Princesa, Palawan, specifically on the mangrove ecosystem. This study focused only on Honda Bay, Snake Island, Palawan. Differences in the species

richness, cover, density, and diversity of coastal resources, specifically the mangroves were analyzed before and after the occurrence of Typhoon Rai (and/or the declaration of DAO No. 2011–12). The output of this study provides an update on the status of mangrove stand structure and composition on the island, as well as the carbon stock using an allometric equation of mangrove forest. Knowledge of the prevailing condition of the resources on an island is an important element in identifying the current research and conservation needs and management strategies.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The literature is growing on the mangrove ecosystem in the world. Numerous studies showed that the diversity and structure of mangroves vary with time, much like those of any other ecosystem. Mangroves and seagrass beds are notable characteristics with significant ecological and economic importance along the tropical coastline (Nagelkerken, 2009; Sy et al., 2014). Mangroves are among the world's most remarkable plant species; they are found along the shores of tropical and subtropical regions and are very resistant of adverse environmental factors including excessive salinity and intense heat (Kathiresan & Bingham, 2001). In 2000, there were 53,190 square miles (137,760 km²) of mangroves left in the globe, covering 118 countries (Ochieng et al., 2011).

Overall importance of mangrove forests

According to Carrasquilla and Juanes (2017), mangroves offer vital ecological services including fisheries, storm and hurricane protection, and carbon sequestration that minimize the effects of climate change. Additionally, fish and invertebrates use mangroves as important nesting sites. Mangroves are an essential part of the recreational fishing business because they provide shrimp, crabs, mollusks, and fish with useful habitats to raise offspring (Duke, 2007). These environments offer an abundant supply of food as well as protection from predators. Endangered and threatened species are supported by mangroves (Bowen, 2001). Some species live throughout their entire lives in mangroves, devouring and breeding there, while others use mangrove systems for at least some portion of their life cycles. Additionally, mangroves provided ecosystem benefits. They are put to use across the world. They may be collected for their durable, water-resistant wood,

tannins, charcoal, and various elements from which medicinal products can be made (Friess, 2019).

Carbon stock in mangroves

Considering mangroves are substantial organic carbon sinks, there is a lot of interest in using them to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Chatting et al. 2020). They may build up biologically rich soils that store organic carbon for a long time and are frequently several meters deep. They have a relatively high capacity to sequester and store carbon in soils and biomass (Donato et al., 2011). According to Donato et al. (2011), mangroves may store up to five times as much organic carbon as tropical mountain forests. Mangroves' capacity to sequester and retain organic carbon, especially in their soils, is greatly enhanced by their high production and slow rates of soil decomposition (Alongi, 2012). Mangroves have aboveground net primary production (NPP) rates of $8.1 \text{ t DW ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which are comparable to the rates of $11.1 \text{ t DW ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ that are extremely productive tropical terrestrial forests (Alongi, 2012).

Threats to mangrove forests

The Philippines' mangrove community faces several threats, including typhoons and sea level rise, as well as impacts from humans such as converting mangrove areas into fish ponds. Additionally, the pressures of economic development and inappropriate use have resulted in an alarming loss of mangrove cover globally. By the end of this century, all mangrove forests that are not protected are expected to have declined. The primary reasons include the expansion of habitable areas for agriculture, aquaculture, and communities in general, as well as

the logging of mangroves for the production of charcoal and timber. However, tourism has been a major factor in their decline as well (Sucharitakul & Hardy, 2021).

Tropical cyclones are an additional threat. These are the most damaging natural disturbances that mangroves encounter; they account for 45% of their naturally occurring mortality and are the main cause of mangrove loss in some areas (Sippo et al. 2018). The features of the coastal environment, such as elevation and historical cyclone frequency, may also have an impact on damage levels, as may the characteristics of the mangrove ecosystems, such as species composition, canopy height, and tree density (Armitage et al. 2019; Walcker et al. 2019; Pennings et al. 2021).

Regeneration potential of mangrove forests

According to Villamayor's 2016 study, which engaged several visits to mangrove sites damaged by severe tropical cyclones, there are significant variations in the degree of survival and recovery based on the type of species assemblage, whether the forest is naturally occurring mixed-species or planted monospecific, and whether or not such stands have already reached specific age-height thresholds.

Significant defoliation, variability in recovery potentials, and the extreme susceptibility of old, homogeneous *Rhizophora* stands are among the effects on the dominant species. Whereas species of *Sonneratia* and *Avicennia* were able to re-leaf, *Rhizophora* species were not.

According to Kauffman and Cole (2010), *Rhizophora* trees lose their capacity for epicormic resprouting at a young age, which means that older individuals are typically unable to recover from severe defoliation, trunk breaking, and de-branching.

According to Ross et al. (2006), *Rhizophora* individuals may not survive within
Species Diversity, Community Structure and Carbon Stock of Mangrove Forest 3-Year 6
Post Occurrence of Typhoon Rai (Odette): The Case of Honda Bay, Snake Island,
Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Philippines

typhoon belts longer than the times between catastrophic typhoons return episodes. In contrast, the long-lived genera *Sonneratia* and *Avicennia* simply resprout after episodic natural pruning (Villamayor, 2016).

Diversity of mangrove ecosystem

Mangroves, with their particular adaptation to the tidal conditions of estuaries and marines, are one of the most prominent coastal ecosystems in the world. They are mostly made up of blooming trees and shrubs. Talking about species diversity and distribution in different areas is about explaining the structure and composition of mangrove ecosystems. It is commonly recognized that mangroves have unique morphological and physiological adaptations that enable them to withstand salt, saturated soils, and frequent tidal flooding. Mangroves are an essential but relatively small portion of the tropical coastal ecology on a global scale (Alappatt 2008).

In the tropical region, mangroves are one of the most diversified categories, especially in the Indo-Malay Philippines archipelago. 46 of the approximately 75 species of mangroves known to science (Spalding et al., 2010) are present in the Philippines, however some have estimated that there are as many as 50 to 60 species (Ximenes, 2015). Mangrove forests are under threat everywhere in the world, as pollution, land clearing; coastal development, natural disasters, and climate change have all contributed to their startling destruction (FAO 2007). In 1918 (Brown & Fischer, 1920), the Philippines' mangrove forests spanned an area of around 450,000 hectares; however, by 2010 (Long et al., 2014), this extent had dropped by 51.8%. The enormous diversity of mangroves on the islands must be preserved by a variety of conservation strategies, such as the restrictive preservation of mangrove areas.

Structural characteristics of mangrove ecosystem

According to estimates, there are around 15.6 million hectares of mangroves worldwide. Mangroves are salt-tolerant evergreen forest ecosystems that are mostly found in tropical and subtropical intertidal zones between roughly 32° N and 38° S latitude (FAO, 2010). To address the contemporary issues confronting mankind, such as food security, pollution, and endangered habitats, ecophysiological studies of mangrove plants—which are adapted to an array of extreme environmental conditions, including salinity, high temperatures, low oxygen, and contaminated environments—are necessary. The characteristics of mangrove wetlands include a salty environment, a humid climate, and muddy or wet soil. According to Selvam and Karunagaran (2004), mangrove plants can withstand salinities ranging from 2‰ to 90‰ and thrive in waterlogged soils. The sizes of mangroves range from barely shrubs to large trees. Mangrove plants have a typical height of 5–25 m (MacNae, 1968), while the age and geographical position of the stands have a major influence (Snedaker, 1978). The flora in the coastal biosphere is directly impacted by the marine climate, which is shaped by several factors such as tides, wave action, saline water, salt spray, and substratum characteristics.

The species richness, diversity, tree/stem density, species and stand basal area, frequency of occurrence of constituent species, plant/stand height, above-ground biomass, and canopy volume/leaf area index are used to define the structure of mangrove vegetation. Plot-less procedures or sample (representative) areas, such as defined plots, can be used to measure these properties. Plant height, apparent plant zonation, and species richness are frequently used in qualitative assessments of vegetation structure.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Among the numerous ecological functions that mangroves offer is protection from storm waves and surges along the shore. Mangroves were extensively restored and planted in tropical and subtropical areas, including the coastal regions of Southeast Asia, as an adaptive strategy for coastal protection. More specifically, during strong storms, breaking trunks, uprooting trees, loosening or shedding of bark, and defoliation are frequent occurrences that might result in the mortality of trees.

This incident may have a negative impact on Snake Island's mangrove ecosystem's general structure and diversity. The distinction between structure, diversity, and carbon stock has not been quantified since Typhoon Rai occurred in 2021. However, this study will evaluate such. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the island's coastal resources, particularly the mangroves, and it was carried out on Snake Island, Honda Bay, and Puerto Princesa, Palawan.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to determine the stand structure and carbon stock of mangrove forests three years after the occurrence of Typhoon Rai in Honda Bay, Snake Island, Puerto Princesa, Palawan. Specifically, it aims to:

- Assess the current and overall condition of the mangrove stand structure on the island.
- Compare the species diversity, community structure, and carbon stock of the island before and after the occurrence of Typhoon Rai (and/or the declaration of DAO No. 2011–12).
- Identify the current research and conservation needs of mangroves.
- Management strategies for the mangrove ecosystem

V. RATIONALE

Mangroves protect coastal areas from storm surges, hurricane winds, waves, and flooding. Mangrove ecosystems are significant, as are the potential implications of their continuous loss. Unfortunately, the pressures of economic expansion and inappropriate use have resulted in a significant decline in mangrove cover worldwide. By the end of this century, all mangrove forests that are not protected may continue to decrease. The primary reasons include the development of habitable areas for agriculture, aquaculture, and communities, as well as the logging of mangroves for the manufacture of charcoal and lumber. However, a major contributing factor to their decrease has also been tourism and natural calamities.

The species diversity, species structure, and biomass carbon stock content of the mangrove vegetation have been assessed in the study that was carried out in 2024 on Honda Bay, Snake Island, Puerto Princesa, Palawan. The data collected was compared to the DENR-ERDB data that was gathered in 2021, which accounts for the 3-year occurrence of Typhoon Rai (Odette).

The conclusions of the study indicate that there is carbon in the mangrove vegetation on Snake Island, Palawan, suggesting that frequent assessments of the area's mangrove cover are necessary in order to maintain and safeguard the island's coastal resources, which depend on mangrove forests. The evaluation of mangroves is essential to ensuring that all those involved are managing the area appropriately to preserve the biodiversity of the island. In doing so, data would be produced and used as the basis for future plans and initiatives.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

One-time sampling was conducted in Honda Bay, Snake Island, and Puerto Princesa in April 2024. Only the mangrove ecosystem was covered in the study. The study was based on secondary as well as primary data. Parameters for primary data collection that were computed are species diversity (overall frequency of the species, diversity indices as well as the listings of species present in the study site), community structure (relative frequency, density, dominance, average basal area, DBH, and height), and the carbon stock.

The secondary data on mangrove structure on the island was requested from the DENR-Ecosystems Research and Development Bureau for comparative analysis of the ecosystem pre- and post-Typhoon Rai. A request letter was drafted and disseminated to ERDB, PENRO Palawan, and the organization of the National Coastal and Marine Center for Research.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Snake Island is located in Honda Bay, Puerto Princesa, Palawan. The island is not a protected area, but human entry is restricted through an administrative order. Based on the current estimates, the island has a land area of 65.45 ha, which includes the mangrove and beach area. In the case of Snake Island, the total mangrove area is 36 hectares (NAMRIA, 2020). On 03 November 2011, the island was designated as the DENR National Coastal and Marine Center for Research through the DENR Administrative Order No.2011-12. There are no settlements in the area. Only the DENR PENRO personnel, who maintain the government facilities in the island and conduct patrolling for unauthorized visits, inhabit the island.

Table 1

Coordinates of the 17 plots established in the island

Station	Longitude	Latitude
1	9° 53' 57.934" N	118° 49' 12.065" E
2	9° 53' 59.608" N	118° 49' 13.321" E
3	9° 54' 4.900" N	118° 49' 20.759" E
4	9° 54' 6.275" N	118° 49' 22.598" E
5	9° 54' 0.778" N	118° 49' 26.526" E
6	9° 53' 55.291" N	118° 49' 27.124" E
7	9° 53' 49.848" N	118° 49' 28.070" E
8	9° 54' 7.848" N	118° 49' 25.954" E
9	9° 54' 10.354" N	118° 49' 28.351" E
10	9° 54' 10.181" N	118° 49' 34.550" E
11	9° 54' 7.628" N	118° 49' 33.787" E
12	9° 54' 12.118" N	118° 49' 38.662" E

13	9° 54' 13.550" N	118° 49' 41.840" E
14	9° 54' 14.728" N	118° 49' 44.627" E
15	9° 54' 16.333" N	118° 49' 47.777" E
16	9° 54' 18.205" N	118° 49' 50.502" E
17	9° 54' 32.141" N	118° 50' 4.571" E

VIII. METHODOLOGY

The 2021 before-Odette assessment data were requested from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources-Ecosystems Research and Development Bureau. A letter was sent to the Provincial Environment and Natural Resource Office in Puerto Princesa, Palawan. The PENR Officer endorsed the letter to the Director of ERDB and granted my requested data.

Field Data Collection

Mangrove extent was plotted on maps. Sampling intensity was determined based on the extent of the mangrove area. Dominant species were noted. A non-destructive quadrat nested quadrat method (English et al., 1997) was employed in the assessment to quantitatively describe the mangrove stand in a total of 17 plots. This method provided information on the species diversity, community structure and C stocks of the mangrove stand. The equipment used is as follows: transect line, measuring tape, caliper, global positioning system (GPS), and a recording slate.

A 10 m x 10 m plot was established along the reforested mangrove area in Snake Island. The distance of each plot was estimated about 100 meters apart where the mangrove species classified, identified, measured and recorded. In each plot, mangrove species larger than 5 cm in diameter were measured and recorded per plot. Parameters such as Total height (estimated from the ground up to the shoot tip); and the Diameter-at-breast height (DBH) (1.3 meter above the ground and diameter above budroot (DAB) equal to 30 cm or .3 meters above the stilt root) were measured.

A 1 m x 1 m subplot was laid out in the center of each plot in order to measure the regeneration capacity of the area. Saplings (those with diameter smaller than 5 cm and height more than 2m) were identified and the number of individuals per species was determined. Actual counts of seedlings (height lower than 2m) were recorded as the number of individuals per species.

At each plot, mangrove species were identified and classified into timber size trees (> 15 cm DBH/DAB), pole size trees (> 5 cm up to 15 cm in DBH/DAB), and regeneration saplings (5 cm DBH/DAB and 2 m in height) or seedlings (height below 2 m). In timber sized trees (>15 cm DBH/DAB), the following parameters were assessed: (1) Total Height (to the nearest 0.5 m) and (2) Diameter at breast height DAB/DBH. The height was estimated directly.

The diameter was measured accurately using caliper and a diameter tape for larger trees. In all species, except for *Rhizophora* spp., diameter was recorded at 1.3 meter height from the ground known as diameter-at- breast height (DBH). In *Rhizophora* spp., because of the presence of stilt roots, the diameter was recorded at a height of 0.3 meter from the topmost stilt roots known as diameter above budroot (DAB). In the case of regeneration saplings and seedlings, the densities (number present in each plot) were recorded per species.

The collected data were analyzed for abundance, dominance, diversity, aboveground biomass among other vegetation variables, as discussed in Kent and Coker (1992); Mueller-Dombois and Ellenberg (1971).

Species Diversity and Community Structure

The dominant species for each site was determined based on the importance value (IV). The IV is the sum of the relative density, relative frequency, and relative dominance. These were computed using the following formula:

Density

$$= (\text{Total number of individuals of species I} / \text{Total area sampled (m}^2\text{)}) 100$$

Relative Density

$$= (\text{Density of species I} / \text{Total density of all species}) 100$$

Basal Area (m²)/Dominance

$$= 0.7854 * \text{DBH}^2 \text{ of species I} / \text{area sampled (m}^2\text{)}$$

Relative Dominance

$$= \text{Basal area of species I} / \text{Basal area of all species}) 100$$

Frequency

$$= (\text{No. of plots where species I occur} / \text{Total number of plots}) 100$$

Relative Frequency

$$= \text{Frequency of a species} / \text{Frequency of all species}) 100$$

Importance Value

$$= \text{Relative density} + \text{Relative dominance} + \text{Relative frequency}$$

Number of individuals was also taken to measure diversity indices: Shannon-Weiner index, Simpson's index, species richness and species evenness. This was computed to compare diversity between sampling periods (before declaration or before Typhoon Rai vs current). Specific mangrove species which increased or decreased in cover were determined by comparing importance values. Diversity indices were computed using the following formulae:

Shannon Diversity Index (H'):
$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^S p_i \ln p_i$$

Where:

H' = the value of the Shannon-Weiner diversity index

S = Number of species in the study area

Pi = the proportion of individuals of each species belonging to the ith species of the total number of individuals

The Abundance of each species was computed as the mean number of individuals per species across the total plots established. The mean value was scaled to a hectare basis.

Biomass Carbon Stock (Total Biomass of Standing Timber)

Aboveground biomass has been calculated in each plot. The tree biomass was calculated from the field measurements of DBH and height and published allometric equations for mangroves from Southeast Asian countries (Chave et al. 2005). The tree biomass data have been converted to its C equivalent using the C fraction value (47% for AGB) based on Kauffman and Donato (2012) and Komiyama et al. (2008).

Figure 1. Biomass allometric equations and wood density value used in the study.

Species	Aboveground	Belowground*	References for aboveground biomass equations	Wood Density (g cm ⁻³)
<i>Aegiceras floridum</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.71 ^a
<i>Bruguiera gymnorrhiza</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.186 D^{2.31}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Clough and Scott (1989)	0.85 ^b
<i>B. parviflora</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.168 D^{2.42}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Clough and Scott (1989)	0.89 ^b
<i>B. sexangula</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.168 D^{2.42}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Clough and Scott (1989)	0.87 ^b
<i>Camptostemon philippinense</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.71 ^a
<i>Ceriops tagal</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.89 ^b
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.7854 * D^2 * H^{1.6}$	Biomass (kg) = $=0.7845 * D^2 * H^{1.6} * 0.04$ (Zamora 1999)	Brown (1997); Zamora (1999)	0.25 ^c
<i>Heritiera littoralis</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.84 ^a
<i>Lumnitzera racemosa</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.71 ^a
<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.235 D^{2.42} + \text{Biomass}_{\text{aerial}}(\text{kg}) = 0.0209 D^{2.55}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Ong <i>et al.</i> (2004)	1.04 ^b
<i>R. mucronata</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.235 D^{2.42} + \text{Biomass}_{\text{aerial}}(\text{kg}) = 0.0209 D^{2.55}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Ong <i>et al.</i> (2004)	0.98 ^b
<i>R. stylosa</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.235 D^{2.42} + \text{Biomass}_{\text{aerial}}(\text{kg}) = 0.0209 D^{2.55}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Ong <i>et al.</i> (2004)	0.98 ^b
<i>Sonneratia alba</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.83 ^b
<i>Xylocarpus moluccensis</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.66 ^b
<i>X. granatum</i>	Biomass (kg) = $0.251 * D^{2.46}$	Biomass (kg) = $0.199 * D^{0.699 D^{2.22}}$	Komiyama <i>et al.</i> (2005)	0.66 ^b

*Howard *et al.*, 2014 ^aBrown and Fisher, 1920 ^bBrown 1997; Zamora, 1999 ^cEquations from Komiyama *et al.* (2005) unless stated otherwise

Statistical Analysis

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant difference in the species diversity and structure of mangroves among plots and in between years (2021 and 2024). This was also used to assess whether there were differences in biomass carbon stocks among plots and years (2021 vs. 2024).

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

SPECIES COMPOSITION

The 17 plots that were laid by ERDB in 2021 were assessed in March 2024 for the purpose of this study with a total area of 1700 m² sampling plots (Figure 2). Sampling intensity was equally distributed within the total mangrove area of 25 hectares. Snake Island in Honda Bay, Palawan, has the National Center for Marine and Coastal Research (NCMCR) located in Palawan, which, as we all know, is the country's last ecological frontier.

Figure 2. Sampling plots in Snake Island.

The area is covered with mangrove strand vegetation. It is a mixed stand as a result of the efforts of DENR, LGU and other agencies that planted more *Rhizophora* Species Diversity, Community Structure and Carbon Stock of Mangrove Forest 3-Year Post Occurrence of Typhoon Rai (Odette): The Case of Honda Bay, Snake Island, Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Philippines

spp. around the island. A total of 7 species belonging to 3 families were recorded in the area. The analysis of the tree flora of the study showed that the family Rhizophoraceae was the most represented, recording the highest number of species. Lythraceae and Acanthaceae species were also present on the island.

Table 2

Species observed in the study site

Family	Common Name	Scientific Name
Acanthaceae	Bungalon	<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forssk.) Vierh.
Lythraceae	Pagatpat	<i>Sonneratia alba</i> Sm.
Rhizophoraceae	Pototan lalaki	<i>Bruguiera cylindrical</i> L.
	Busain	<i>Bruguiera gymnorhiza</i> (L.) Lam. ex Savigny
	Tangal	<i>Ceriops tagal</i> (Perr.) C.B. Robinsons
	Bakauan babae	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i> Lam.
	Bakauan bato	<i>Rhizophora stylosa</i> (Griff.) Schimp.

Figure 3. Species found in the island (A. *Rhizophora stylosa*, B. *Rhizophora mucronata*, C. *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza*, D. *Bruguiera cylindrica*, E. *Ceriops tagal*, F. *Sonneratia alba*, G. *Avicennia marina*).

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Diameter-at-breast-Height (DBH), Height, and Basal Area

In Table 4, the average DBH (cm) and height (m) of the species present in the study site were listed. It has been observed that *A. marina* and *R. stylosa* resulted in the species with the highest average Basal Area and DBH. In terms of average height, *S. alba* bore the highest mean. Among the rather limited group of halophytic higher plants that inhabit the intertidal zone at the border between land and water, mangroves are the only trees. *A. marina* and *R. stylosa* are the two of the more prevalent mangrove species. Both species were found growing at or close to the seaward border of bays and estuaries, where they are frequently subjected to flooding from the seawater (Do et al. 2019). *S. alba* has been shown to be a better species for the restoration in sandy borders. This type of mangrove is appropriate to plant near the coastal front because it is more resilient, larger, and resistant to the forces of nature (Trangia, 2022).

Table 3

Mean Basal Area, DBH and Height of species present in the area

Species	Mean Basal Area	Mean DBH (cm)	Mean Height (m)
<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forssk.) Vierh.	0.008	9.166	4.725
<i>Rhizophora stylosa</i> (Griff.) Schimp.	0.007	8.668	4.374
<i>Sonneratia alba</i> Sm.	0.006	8.401	4.858
<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i> Lam.	0.004	7.335	3.767
<i>Bruguiera gymnorrhiza</i> (L.) Lam. ex Savigny	0.004	7.000	3.000
<i>Ceriops tagal</i> (Perr.) C.B. Robinsons	0.004	7.000	3.000
<i>Bruguiera cylindrica</i> L.	0.003	6.000	3.000

Species abundance/density

In terms of species abundance, *R. stylosa* bore the highest among other species. A total of 482 tree individuals of *R. stylosa*, 63 tree individuals of *A. marina*, and 18 individuals of *S. alba*, 2 individuals of *B. gymnorhiza* and *R. mucronata* and an individual species both of *B. cylindrical* and *C. tagal* were measured within the 17 plots. *R. stylosa* is the most abundant mangrove species due to the presence of numerous mother trees, favorable environmental conditions which facilitates its growth and survival. Furthermore, practically all of the mangrove tree planting activities that have taken place on the island in the past are more of the species of *R. stylosa*.

Referring to the abundance of *R. stylosa*, it may have favorable effects. These mangrove species' existence along the shore may be advantageous to the ecosystem. This species has the potential to be utilized as a plant that absorbs heavy metals found in coastal environments. Usually, it is found on the coastline of mangrove ecosystems (Yunasfi et al., 2021). The prop roots and frequent tidal inundation of *Rhizophora* forests served as good nursery habitat for fish, crustaceans, and mollusks (Davis et al., 2014).

Two of the environmental factors often seen in mangrove ecosystems that are proposed to be the drivers of mangrove vegetation are salinity and inundation dynamics. In order to respond physiologically to environmental perturbations, *R. stylosa* has increased their intake of water and removed salt from their water (Hastuti, 2023). It does not alter the amount of water absorbed since it has a system for controlling salt levels that involves building up salt in the plant environment by ultrafiltration of the roots before it is absorbed (Basyuni et al. 2014).

Figure 4. Species abundance at the study site.

Importance Value

Using its relative density, relative basal area, and relative frequency in a study plot or area, the Important Value Index was calculated to quantify the dominance and ecological success of any species with a single value (Faridah et al. 2012). Each species' total contribution to the community was taken into account when calculating the IV. Higher density values correspond to higher numbers of individuals detected. In the study site, the mangrove species of *R. stylosa* was found to have the highest average stem density (482 ha⁻¹) and highest relative density of 84.71%, followed by *A. marina* (11.07%), and *S. alba* (3.16%). The number of plots where a given species of mangrove is present is correlated with its frequency value. Given that *R. stylosa* is equally dispersed throughout all of the plots, it frequently exhibits the

greatest frequency of occurrence in the results of the study (Table 4). Due to its uniform distribution or presence throughout every plot, *R. stylosa* has the highest relative frequency (51.52%) compared to other species. The dominant species in a community possessed values of great importance. The highest value of the *R. stylosa* importance index (IVI) indicated that it contributes relatively significantly to preserving the sustainability of the mangrove ecosystem in the study area. Here, *R. stylosa* displayed one of the highest mean basal areas and the highest IVI of 219.85%, followed by *A. marina* at 38.42% and *S. alba* at 25.01%.

Table 4

Relative values and dominance of the species in the study site

Species	Freq	Den	Dom	RF	RD	RDom	IV
<i>Avicennia marina</i>	6	63	0.35	18.18	11.07	9.16	38.42
<i>Bruguiera cylindrica</i>	1	1	0.00	3.03	0.18	0.07	3.28
<i>Bruguiera gymnorhiza</i>	1	2	0.01	3.03	0.35	0.23	3.61
<i>Ceriops tagal</i>	1	1	0.00	3.03	0.18	0.10	3.31
<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	2	2	0.00	6.06	0.35	0.11	6.52
<i>Rhizophora stylosa</i>	17	482	3.18	51.52	84.71	83.62	219.85
<i>Sonneratia alba</i>	6	18	0.25	15.15	3.16	6.69	25.01
TOTAL	34	569	3.80	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00

***Note: Frequency (Freq), Density (Den), Dominance (Dom), Relative Frequency (RF), Relative Density (RD), Relative Dominance (RDom), Importance Value (IV)

The mangrove forest was dominated by *R. stylosa*, since the area was an afforestation site of the government using *Rhizophora spp.* This species was observed in all 17 sampling plots. Furthermore, the *R. stylosa* has height and growth that are closely correlated with the environment in which it grows and the conditions under which it does so. For this reason, *R. stylosa* dwarfs are found in ecosystems

with a lower temperature and varying daily sun exposure, although they may grow up to 30 meters in height in locations close to the equator (Nasir, 2007). Due to its location in Palawan, Philippines, Snake Island receives constant direct sunlight, which is beneficial for this species.

When *R. stylosa* coexists with other mangrove species in mangrove ecosystems, it frequently creates monotypic stands. Most frequently, they are seen mixed with *A. marina* and *A. mucronata*. Its capacity to adapt to a variety of temperatures and soil conditions allows it to spread across a large area. Along with corals, muddy, sandy, and rocky soils are also home to their growth. Due to their anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antipyretic properties, these mangrove species are also frequently utilized in traditional medicine (Kalasuba et al., 2023).

Table 5

Mangrove species present in each sampling station

SPECIES	PLOT																
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
<i>Avicennia marina</i>			X	X	X			X	X	X							
<i>Bruguiera cylindrica</i>				X													
<i>Bruguiera gymnorhiza</i>				X													
<i>Ceriops tagal</i>				X													
<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>													X			X	
<i>Rhizophora stylosa</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Sonneratia alba</i>			X	X	X			X	X	X							

SPECIES DIVERSITY

Using the Shannon-Weiner Diversity Index, Table 6 presents the species diversity (H') for each plot of mangrove. Station 4 has 6 of the 7 mangrove species found on the island. This plot contains the most species and is the most diverse among the plots, with an index of 1.081 in 2024 from 1.109 in 2021, but the computed diversity is still in the category of a very low diversity index. Station 10 has the second highest diversity index of 0.9986 in 2024 and 0.9967 in 2021, with an evenness of 0.9048 and 0.8764, respectively. The plots with the highest diversity are populated by three different species: *S. alba*, *A. marina*, and *R. stylosa*. The island's 17 plots assessed in 2024 had mean diversity and evenness values of 0.3219 and 0.8709, respectively.

Since the mangrove stand in the study site had a limited number of mangrove species and was dominated by a few species, the Shannon-Wiener's diversity index (H') value of the mangrove community of Snake Island was quite low when compared to other natural mangrove forests. As a result of their distinct stand formation and harsh coastal environment, mangroves have far less diversity than tropical lowland rainforests (Rasquinha & Mishra, 2021). This is due to the fact that few species in mangroves have developed distinctive adaptations of their own.

Table 6

Species Diversity of Mangroves in Snake Island in between 2021 and 2024

Station	2021				2024			
	No. of Species	No. of Individuals	Shannon (H)	Evenness	No. of Species	No. of Individuals	Shannon (H)	Evenness
1	1	24	0	1	1	22	0	1
2	1	77	0	1	1	77	0	1
3	3	30	1.063	0.7277	3	16	0.8647	0.7915

4	6	35	1.109	0.505	6	32	1.081	0.4911
5	2	18	0.6931	1	2	16	0.6853	0.9922
6	1	55	0	1	1	55	0	1
7	1	3	0	1	1	3	0	1
8	3	41	0.7574	0.7109	3	39	0.7259	0.6889
9	3	33	0.9348	0.8489	3	26	0.9078	0.8263
10	3	22	0.9667	0.8764	3	20	0.9986	0.9048
11	1	37	0	1	1	34	0	1
12	1	43	0	1	1	42	0	1
13	2	51	0.09651	0.5507	2	51	0.09651	0.5507
14	1	26	0	1	1	25	0	1
15	1	41	0	1	1	39	0	1
16	2	43	0.1105	0.5584	2	42	0.1125	0.5595
17	1	33	0	1	1	30	0	1

In terms of plots, Plots 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, and 10 have the observed differences in their diversity. Plot 3 shows the largest differences in diversity between 2021 and 2024. In terms of the data increase from 2021 to 2024, only Plot 10 resulted in an increase in diversity from 2021 to 2024 with an index of 0.9667 to 0.9986 and an evenness value of 0.8764 to 0.9048.

Figure 5. Species Diversity of the 17 Plots in Snake Island Between 2021 and 2024.

BIOMASS CARBON STOCK

Results of this study revealed that the biomass carbon stock of mangroves in Snake Island ranged from 1.59 to 257.38 MgC ha⁻¹, or a mean of 75.56 MgC ha⁻¹, in 2021 and 2024. They differ only at the mean biomass carbon stock by 0.21MgC ha⁻¹. As observed in the analysis of the total biomass carbon stock, among the plots, only Plot 1 differs from 2021 to 2024 assessment by 3.6 MgC ha⁻¹. The 2024 assessment revealed a total biomass carbon stock of 34.2 MgC ha⁻¹ while 2021 was 30.6 MgC ha⁻¹.

For the computed biomass C stock both in 2021 and 2024, Plot 2 bore the highest with a total of 257.38 MgC ha⁻¹, probably because of the higher mean DBH and stem density of 10.77 and 0.752 respectively, as compared to the other sampling plots, resulting in a bigger biomass and it was purely a *R. stylosa* stand.

Plots 6, 11, and 17 are among the plots with the highest biomass C stock, with a total of 112.42 MgC ha⁻¹, 113.35 MgC ha⁻¹, and 115.48 MgC ha⁻¹, respectively.

Mangroves face major issues such as deforestation, degradation, aquaculture rise, overharvesting, escalating salinity, and climate change, including the occurrence of strong typhoons (Pearson et al., 2013; Polidoro et al., 2014; Rahman et al., 2020). Mangroves face global problems that impact species diversity, forest structure, and ecological functions, resulting in changes in biomass and carbon stocks (McGowan et al., 2010; Maiti and Chowdhury, 2013; Oland et al., 2017).

Figure 6. Total Biomass C stock (MgC ha⁻¹) of each of the sampling plots.

In terms of biomass carbon stock per species, *R. stylosa* bore the highest in the 2024 assessment, while *R. mucronata* bore the lowest with 0.49 MgC ha⁻¹. *R. stylosa* obtained the highest value because of its dominance giving a huge trunk diameter and height. As a result, as tree biomass increases, so does carbon

absorption. Furthermore, the higher the mangrove density, the higher the carbon content, whereas stand density, composition, and structure, as well as the quality of mangrove growth sites, all influence the rise in biomass and carbon content of mangrove trees. *A. marina* and *S. alba* decreased their total biomass carbon stock from 2021 to 2024, while *C. tagal* and *B. cylindrica* did not change. The *R. stylosa* has the highest increase in the total value. However, *B. gymnorhiza* increases only by 0.04 MgC ha⁻¹ from 2021 to 2024.

Table 7

Total Biomass C stock (MgC ha⁻¹) per species

Species	2021			2024		
	AGB/ha	BGB/ha	Total	AGB/ha	BGB/ha	Total
<i>Rhizophora stylosa</i>	1.65	0.48	2.13	1.65	12.61	14.26
<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	0.34	0.15	0.49	0.34	0.15	0.49
<i>Ceriops tagal</i>	0.71	0.29	1.00	0.71	0.29	1.00
<i>Avicennia marina</i>	1.29	0.50	1.79	1.25	0.48	1.73
<i>Bruguiera cylindrica</i>	0.48	0.21	0.69	0.48	0.21	0.69
<i>Bruguiera gymnorhiza</i>	2.53	0.40	2.93	2.53	0.44	2.97
<i>Sonneratia alba</i>	4.63	1.54	6.17	4.49	1.51	6.00

Stocking classification

The DENR (1998) stocking categorization classified a forest as adequately, inadequately stock, and logged-over areas, while the FAO (1996) classified the forest cover density as highly dense, sparse density cover, and logged-over or cleared areas (Table 8). DBH greater than 5 cm had a total density of 2,935 trees/ha (Table 9).

All of the sampling plots fall under the category of adequately stock or have highly dense forest cover. Only Plots 2 and 7 have the category of cleared area in the assessment conducted in 2024. With this, we can say that there is no need for reforestation or afforestation activities.

Table 8

The DENR (1998) and FAO (1996) stocking categorization based on mangrove density (individuals ha⁻¹)

Density	DENR (1998)	FAO (1996)
1,500 above	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
625-1,499	Inadequately stock	Sparse density cover
Below 625	Logged-over area	Logged-over/cleared area

Table 9

Mangrove density (Trees ha⁻¹) and classification of the sampling site

Plot	2021 SURVEY			2024 SURVEY		
	Density	DENR (1998)	FAO (1996)	Density	DENR (1998)	FAO (1996)
1	6200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	2200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
2	300	Logged-over area	Logged-over/cleared area	300	Logged-over area	Logged-over/cleared area
3	1700	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	1600	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover

4	7600	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	3100	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
5	3200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	1500	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
6	3400	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	6200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
7	4200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	300	Logged-over area	Logged-over/cleared area
8	3300	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	3900	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
9	2100	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	2600	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
10	4200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	2000	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
11	5100	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	3400	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
12	2500	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	4200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
13	4100	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	5100	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
14	4300	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	2400	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
15	2300	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	3900	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
16	3700	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	4200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover
17	3200	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover	3000	Adequately stock	Highly dense cover

MANGROVE COVER BETWEEN 2021 and 2024

From the 612 monitoring tree individuals before Typhoon Rai in December 2021 down to the 569 tree individuals monitored 3 years post-typhoon. Initially, a total of 4 individuals were dead, and 39 were top-pruned, as reported by ERDB in December 2021. These 39 individuals did not recover based on the last assessment conducted in the first quarter of 2024. It was observed that four plots (Plots 2, 6, 7, and 13) on Snake Island had no damage at all. Among the plots, Plot 3 has the highest mortality rate, with a total of 14 trees, mostly *R. stylosa* and *A. marina*. Most of the plots located facing seaward have higher mortality rate.

The decline in mangrove species observed in the regular survey and monitoring on Snake Island in 2021 compared to this season (3 years after the occurrence of Typhoon Rai) was the focus of the survey, and this was the mangrove species present inside the permanent monitoring stations established by ERDB.

Table 10

Comparative data on the structure of Snake Island 3-year post occurrence of Typhoon Rai

Plot	2021 Survey (Before Odette)			2024 Survey			2021 (after Odette)	2024 (3-year post occurrence)
	Number of Trees	Mean DBH	Mean Height	Number of Trees	Mean DBH	Mean Height		
1	24	7.57	3.13	22	7.65	3.09	2 Top pruned	2 Dead
2	77	10.77	4.88	77	10.77	4.88	No damage	-
3	30	9.40	4.90	16	8.81	4.83	14 Damaged	14 Dead
4	35	7.46	2.94	32	7.52	3.00	3 Dead	3 Dead
5	18	9.06	3.19	16	7.97	2.84	2 Top pruned	2 Dead
6	55	9.02	4.15	55	9.02	4.15	No damage	-
7	3	5.33	2.00	3	5.33	2.00	No damage	-

8	41	8.41	5.39	39	8.26	5.23	2 Top pruned	2 Dead
9	33	8.06	5.21	26	7.81	5.04	6 Top pruned	6 Dead
10	22	10.61	7.05	20	10.33	6.81	2 Top pruned	2 Dead
11	37	10.36	5.16	34	10.56	5.17	3 Top pruned	3 Dead
12	43	8.54	4.37	42	8.54	4.37	1 Dead	1 Dead
13	51	7.59	4.41	51	7.59	4.41	No damage	-
14	26	7.92	3.27	25	7.98	3.28	1 Top pruned	1 Dead
15	41	6.63	3.29	39	6.64	3.28	2 Top pruned	2 Dead
16	43	7.71	4.47	42	7.74	4.48	1 Top pruned	1 Dead
17	33	9.36	4.36	30	9.33	4.43	3 Top pruned	3 Dead
	612	8.46	4.24	569.00	8.34	4.19		43 Dead Trees

Figure 7. Some of the pruned and dead trees observed in the island.

On December 17, typhoon Odette made landfall for the 8th time at La Libertad, Negros Oriental. It then traversed the Visayan Sea and, with significantly weaker gusts, made landfall for the last time in Roxas, Palawan. It left the West Philippine Sea after traveling through the island. Typhoon Odette's (Rai) center of

eye was situated west-northwest of Puerto Princesa City, Palawan, on December 18, and it was heading towards the West Philippine Sea.

Typhoon Rai caused significant damage in Palawan. Super Typhoon Rai, also known as Odette, is the country's most powerful typhoon and was ranked one of the seven strongest typhoons in the world in 2021 (Cahigas, 2023). The typhoon devastated various areas including Palawan (Forest Foundation Philippines, 2023). Typhoon Odette severely destroyed Palawan's mangroves, causing uprooting and defoliation. The devastation was significant, impacting an estimated 6,447 hectares, or 50% of the region's entire mangrove area (Forest Foundation Philippines, 2023). The mangroves at Puerto Princesa account for 11.7% of Palawan's total mangrove area (5995 hectares) (Dangan-Galon et al., 2016).

In Snake Island, mangrove forests are mostly found in the south-west part of the island, where they are equally dispersed along the shoreline. In addition to protecting the coastline, it provides a natural dwelling for fish and invertebrates that are valuable for industry, including mangrove crabs (*Scylla serrata*). In addition to the common crab that is observed on the island, there was also the horseshoe crab (*Tachypleus tridentatus*), also known as a "living fossil" (Padin & Natividad, 2017).

Figure 8. Mangrove cover in 2021.

Figure 9. Mangrove cover in 2023.

Given the destruction caused by the typhoon throughout Palawan, the 3-year post-evaluation of Snake Island revealed only a 7.03 % decrease. This is most likely due to the observation that new shoots and stems regenerated from the destroyed mangrove trees, resulting in an increase of 0.63 hectares in mangrove cover on the island. Given the stated mortality rate in the 2024 assessment, the mangrove cover rises from 18.43 hectares to 19.06 ha through natural regeneration (Figure 8 & 9).

Mangrove forests are often regenerated by natural regeneration or artificial restoration with planted seedlings. Most native species occupy the coastline as a result of natural recolonization, allowing for natural succession (Macintosh, 2002). The primary benefit of natural regeneration is that the emerging forest is predicted to be more closely related to the native mangrove species. Furthermore, natural regeneration is very basic yet strongly generated; minimal effort is required, resulting in less soil disturbance.

Figure 10. Regeneration in parts of the mangrove area on the island.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Diversity

In order to determine whether there is a significant difference between the years, the diversity of the data collected in 2024 and the data retrieved from ERDB in 2021 was evaluated using the Analysis of Variance. The normality and homogeneity tests were performed on the data prior to the ANOVA since they have an impact on the validity of the test findings and are crucial factors to take into account when using a t-test.

According to Mishra et al. (2019), the assumption that the variances of the several groups under comparison are roughly equal is known as homogeneity of variance. In cases when variations lack homogeneity, the t-test may yield imprecise outcomes. The variances of the two groups being compared should be equal for the independent sample t-test, which makes this significant.

Also, the presumption that data is representative of a population with a normal distribution is known as data normality. The t-test, which assumes that the data follows a normal distribution, may not be acceptable when the data is not normally distributed. Variations in normality may have an impact on the t-test's Type I error rate, often known as the false positive rate.

To summarize, the reliability and correctness of the t-test findings are dependent on the homogeneity of variance and normality of the data sets, which permits acceptable statistical inferences to be made from the data.

Given the results of the homogeneity and normality tests, it has been observed that the data are homogeneous and normal. In terms of year (2021 vs.

2024), it was found that the data obtained in 2021 were not significantly different from the data gathered in 2024.

Table 11

ANOVA of Shannon Diversity Index between 2021 and 2024

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Year	0.00197	1	0.00197	0.00999	0.921
Residuals	6.30632	32	0.19707		
T-Test					
					0.921
Normality Test					
					<0.001
Homogeneity Test					
					0.717

On the other hand, the data were significantly different from all of the data sets in between plots. It has been observed that the 2021 and 2024 data do not have a huge difference from each other. Plots 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, and 10 differ in their observed diversity from one another. Plot 3 illustrates the biggest change in diversity between 2021 and 2024, but only Plot 10 showed an increase in diversity from 2021 to 2024 in terms of data analysis, with an index of 0.9667 to 0.9986 and an evenness value of 0.8764 to 0.9048.

Table 12*ANOVA of the Shannon Diversity Index between Plots*

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Plot	6.2868	16	0.39293	311	<0.001
Residual	0.0215	17	0.00126		

Biomass Carbon Stock

According to the ANOVA results, there were no appreciable changes in the biomass carbon stock between 2021 and 2024. With a total of 257.38 MgC ha⁻¹ for plot 2, the computed biomass C stock in both 2021 and 2024 bore the highest. This was purely a *R. stylosa* stand likely due to the higher mean DBH and stem density of 10.77 and 0.752, respectively, compared to the other sampling plots.

Table 13*ANOVA of Biomass Carbon Stock between 2021 and 2024*

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Year	0.381/	1	0.381	1.21 e -4	0.991
Residuals	100968.113	32	3155.254		
T-Test					
					0.991
Normality Test					
					<0.001
Homogeneity Test					
					0.993

Significant differences among plots were observed from the data on biomass carbon stock due to the number of individuals per plot with differences in basal area

and height. Plot 3 has a significant decrease in terms of average biomass carbon stock, resulting in 14 dead trees from 2021 to 2024.

Table 14

ANOVA of the Biomass Carbon Stock between Plots

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Plot	100962.01	16	6310.126	16554	<.001
Residual	6.48	17	0.381		

X. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

One-time sampling was conducted in March 2024 to compare the data on species diversity, structure, and carbon stock with the data gathered by DENR-ERDB before Typhoon Rai (Odette) occurred in 2021. The 17 plots established by DENR-ERDB in 2021 were assessed during the survey this year. A total of 7 species belonging to 3 families were recorded in the area. The analysis of the tree flora of the study showed that the family of Rhizophoraceae was the most represented, recording the highest number of species. Lythraceae and Acanthaceae species were also present on the island. In terms of species abundance, *R. stylosa* bore the highest among other species. A total of 482 tree individuals in *Rhizophora stylosa*, 63 tree individuals of *A. marina*, and 18 individuals from *S. alba* were among the species recorded on the island with the highest abundance. It has also been observed that *Avicennia marina* and *Rhizophora stylosa* have the highest average basal area and DBH, giving them the highest importance value among other species with 219.85% and 38.42%, respectively.

This also gives a category of adequately stock or has highly dense forest cover, resulting in a little difference to the biomass carbon stock of 0.21 MgC ha⁻¹ from 2021 to 2024. The species *Rhizophora stylosa* was the highest contributor to this amount of carbon stock, with a value of 219.85% and a total biomass carbon stock of 2.13 to 14.26 MgC ha⁻¹ from 2021 to 2024. Seven species were recorded on the island that fall under the category of least concern species under the IUCN.

It was revealed that only 43 individuals were considered dead from the hit of the typhoon, owing only to a 7.03% decrease. Given the stated mortality rate in the 2024 assessment, the mangrove cover rises from 18.43 hectares to 19.06 hectares

through natural regeneration. This implies that instead of planting and allowing nature to take its course when it comes to mangrove regeneration following natural disturbances, it could be easier and preferable to exhibit patience in ensuring the proper conditions for natural colonization by propagules. Mangroves regenerate through several processes, and in highly damaged areas, this process may take longer than in less disturbed areas. On the other hand, the mangroves showed remarkable resilience in the midst of a major disturbance such as Typhoon Rai, since they were able to withstand the damage caused by the typhoon. With regard to Snake Island, there was no disturbance until November 3, 2011, when the DENR issued DAO No. 2011-12, ordering the island to be designated as the National Coastal and Marine Center for Research (NCMCR) and prohibiting any activities unrelated to research.

For the statistical analysis conducted from the data obtained in 2021 and gathered in 2024, in terms of diversity between years 2021 and 2024, it was found that the data obtained in 2021 were not significantly different from the data gathered in 2024 ($p = 0.921$), but there is a significant difference among plots due to the number of individuals in each plot ($p = 0.001$).

Considering the biomass carbon stock, the data collected in 2021 and 2024 did not show a significant difference between the years ($p = 0.991$). However, the number of individuals in each plot showed a significant variation between the plots ($p = <0.001$).

These results imply that there is a need to continuously assess the current status of mangroves on the island in order to help maintain the ecosystem as well as the coastal resources that depend on mangrove forests. The mangrove vegetation of

Snake Island, Palawan, contains carbon from the standing timber. Knowing the diversity, structure, and carbon stock content of the island gave information to maintain the biodiversity conservation of the area. These generate data and provide the framework for the next programs and initiatives that can be conducted on the island.

REFERENCES

- Alappatt, J.P. (2008). Chapter 5 - Structure and Species Diversity of Mangrove Ecosystem, Biodiversity and Climate Change Adaptation in Tropical Islands. Academic Press, Pages 127-144, ISBN 9780128130643, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813064-3.00005-3>.
- Alongi, D.M. (2002). Present state and future of the world's mangrove forests. *Environmental Conservation*. 29 (3): 331–349. DOI: 10.1017/S0376892902000231.
- Alongi, D.M. (2012). Carbon sequestration in mangrove forests. *Carbon Management*. 3, 313–322. doi: 10.4155/cmt.12.20.
- Armitage AR, Weaver CA, Kominoski JS, and Pennings SC. (2019). Resistance to hurricane effects varies among wetland vegetation types in the marsh-mangrove ecotone. *Estuaries and Coasts* 43: 960–70.
- Basyuni M., Putri L. A. P., Nainggolan B., Sihaloho P. E.(2014). Growth and biomass in response to salinity and subsequent fresh water in mangrove seedlings *Avicennia marina* and *Rhizophora stylosa*. *Journal of Tropical Forest Management* 20(1):17- 25.
- Brown, W.H. and A.F. Fischer. (1920). Philippine mangrove swamps. In: Minor products of Philippine forests, Brown W.H. (Ed.), pp. 9– 125, Bureau of Forestry Bull. No. 22, Bureau of Printing, Manila.
- Bryan-Brown, D. N. (2020). Global trends in mangrove forest fragmentation. Scientific Report. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-63880-1>.
- Carrasquilla-Henao, M. & Juanes, F. (2017). Mangroves enhance local fisheries catches: a global meta-analysis. *Fish and Fisheries*. 18, 79–93.
- Cesar H. (2000). Impacts of the 1998 coral bleaching event on tourism in El Nido, Philippines. U.S. Department of State, East Asia and Pacific Environmental Initiative.
- Chatting, M., Le Vay, L., Walton, M., Skov, M. W., Kennedy, H., Wilson, S., et al. (2020). Mangrove carbon stocks and biomass partitioning in an extreme environment. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*. 244:106940. doi: 10.1016/j.ecss.2020.10694.
- Dalby J. and Sorensen TK. (2002). Coral reef resource management in the Philippines, with a focus on marine protected areas as a management tool, University of Copenhagen.
- Davis, J, Pitt, K, Fry, B, Olds, A and Connolly, R (2014), 'Seascape-scale trophic links for fish on inshore coral reefs', *Coral Reefs*. [online], vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 897-907. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00338-014-1196-4>.

- del Valle, A., Eriksson, M., and Ishizawa, O. A. Miranda, J. J. (2020). Mangroves protect coastal economic activity from hurricanes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. U.S.A. 117, 265–270.
- Do, B., Koedam, N. & Triest, L. (2019). *Avicennia marina* maintains genetic structure whereas *Rhizophora stylosa* connects mangroves in a flooded, former inner sea (Vietnam). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*. 222. 10.1016/j.ecss.2019.04.005.
- Donato, D. C., Kauffman, J. B., Murdiyarso, D., Kurnianto, S., Stidham, M., and Kanninen, M. (2011). Mangroves are among the most carbon-rich forests in the tropics. *Nature Geoscience*. 4, 293–297. doi: 10.1038/ngeo1123.
- Duke, N. C. et al. (2007). A world without mangroves?. *Science* 317, 41–43.
- English S., Wilkinson C., and Baker V. (1994). Survey manual for tropical marine resources. Townsville, Australia: Australian Institute of Marine Science.
- FAO. (2007). The World's Mangroves, 1980–2005 FAO Forestry Paper No. 153. Pp. 1-77.
- Faridah-Hanum, I.; Kudus, K.A.; Saari, N.S. Plant Diversity and Biomass of Marudu Bay Mangroves in Malaysia. *Pakistan J. Bot.* 2012, 44, 151–156. [Google Scholar].
- Forest Management Bureau (FMB). (2013). Philippine Forest Facts and Figures. FMB Building, Visayas Avenue, Quezon City, Philippines. Retrieved from: https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/pdf/ref/PF3_2013.pdf.
- Fortes, M.D. (2013). A review: biodiversity, distribution, and conservation of Philippine seagrass. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 95–111.
- Friess, D.A. (2019). The state of the world's mangrove forests: past, present, and future. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*. 44, 89–115.
- Garcia K., Gevaña D., and Malabrigo P. (2013). Philippines' Mangrove Ecosystem: Status, Threats, and Conservation. 10.1007/978-1-4614-8582-7_5.
- Giri C, Ochieng E, Loveland T, Zhu Z, Singh A, et al. (2011). Status and distribution of mangrove forests in the world using earth observation satellite data. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* (20):154–159.
- Hastuti E. D., Izzati M., Prihastanti E. (2023). Water uptake and salt accumulation under *Rhizophora stylosa* seedling planted in controlled salinity and inundation levels. *AAFL Bioflux* 16(2):1069-1076.
- Kathiresan, K. and Bingham, B.L. (2001), *Biology of Mangroves and Mangrove Ecosystems*. *Advances in Marine Biology*, 40, 81-251.
- Kathiresan K., Bingham BL. (2001). *Biology of mangroves and mangrove ecosystems*. *Advances in Marine Biology*, 40:81–251.

- Kauffman, J.B. and Donato, D. (2012). Protocols for the measurement, monitoring, and reporting of structure, biomass, and carbon stocks in mangrove forests.
- Komiyama A, Ong JE, and Pongpan S. (2008). Allometry, biomass, and productivity of mangrove forests: A review. *Aquat Bot* 89: 128–137.
- Lagomasino D., Fatoyinbo T., Castaneda-Moya E., et al. (2021). Storm surge and ponding explain mangrove dieback in southwest Florida following Hurricane Irma. *Nature Communications* 12: 4003.
- Lee SY, Primavera JH, Guebas FD, MvKee K, Bosire JO, et al. (2014) Ecological role and services of tropical mangrove ecosystems: a reassessment. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 23(7): 726-743.
- Long, J., Napton, D., Giri, C. and J. Graesser. 2014. A mapping and monitoring assessment of the Philippines' mangrove forests from 1990 to 2010. *Journal of Coastal Research* 30(2): 260–271.
- Macreadie, P. I. et al. (2019). The future of blue-carbon science. *Nature Communications*. 10, 1–13.
- Mayaux P, Holmgren P, Achard F, Eva H, Stibig HJ, and Branthomme A. (2005). Tropical forest covers change in the 1990s and options for future monitoring. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. 2005;360 (1454):373–384.
- Menendez, P., Losada, I. J., Torres-Ortega, S., Narayan, S. & Beck, M. W. (2020). The global food protection benefits of mangroves. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 1–11.
- Nagelkerken (2009). *Ecological Connectivity among Tropical Coastal Ecosystems*, C _ Springer Science + Business Media B.V.
- Pennings SC, Glazner RM, Hughes ZJ, et al. 2021. Effects of mangrove cover on coastal erosion during a hurricane in Texas, USA. *Ecology* 102: e03309.
- Primavera, J. (2004). Philippine mangroves: status, threats and sustainable development [Book chapter]. In M. Vannucci (Ed.), *Mangrove Management and Conservation: Present and Future*. United Nations University Press. <http://hdl.handle.net/10862/480>.
- Primavera JH and Esteban JMA. (2008). A review of mangrove rehabilitation in the Philippines: success, failures and future prospects. *Wetlands Ecological Management*. 16:345-358.
- Rasquinha, D.N.; Mishra, D.R. Tropical cyclones shape mangrove productivity gradients in the Indian subcontinent. *Sci. Rep.* 2021, 11, 1–12. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef].
- Sippo JZ, Lovelock CE, Santos IR, et al. (2018). Mangrove mortality in a changing climate: an overview. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Science* 215: 241-49.

- Spalding, M., Kainuma, M. and L. Collins. 2010. World Atlas of Mangroves. A collaborative project of ITTO, ISME, FAO, UNEP-WCMC, UNESCO-MAB, UNU-INWEH and TNC. London (UK): Earthscan, London. 319 pp.
- Spalding M, McIvor A, Tonneijck FH, Tol S and van Eijk P. (2014). Mangroves for coastal defense. Guidelines for coastal managers & policy makers. Wetlands International and the Nature Conservancy. 42 pp.
- Taillie PJ, Roman-Cuesta R, Lagomasino D, et al. (2020). Widespread mangrove damage resulting from the 2017 Atlantic mega-hurricane season. *Environmental Research Letters* 15: 064010.
- Thomas N, Lucas R, Bunting P, Hardy A, Rosenqvist A, Simard M (2017) Distribution and drivers of global mangrove forest change, 1996–2010. *PLoS ONE* 12(6): e0179302. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179302>.
- Valiela, I., Bowen, J. L. & York, J. K. (2001). Mangrove forests: One of the world's threatened major tropical environments. *Bioscience* 51, 807–815.
- Walcker R, Laplanche C, Herteman M, et al. (2019). Damages caused by Hurricane Irma in the human-degraded mangroves of Saint Martin (Caribbean). *Sci Rep-UK* 9: 18971.
- Ximenes, A.C. 2015. Global mangrove mapping: a critical tool for conservation. *GLP News*.
- Yunasfi et al 2021 IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 912 012060.
- Zhang, K. et al. (2012). The role of mangroves in attenuating storm surges. *Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Science*. 102–103, 11–23.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

Status of mangrove before typhoon Odette

APPENDIX B

Status of mangrove 3 years after typhoon Odette

APPENDIX C

Suffocation of sand resulting to higher mortality

